

Ion Exchange in Mixed Solvents. Monovalent Cations on a Chelating Resin

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The ion exchange behaviour of Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ on Dowex A-1 (an iminodiacetic acid type chelating resin) in NH_4^+ form has been studied in the presence of water-miscible solvents: methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 2-propanol and acetone. The order of selectivities in aqueous medium, viz., $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ which is the reverse to that observed on sulfonic acid exchangers, has been found to reverse in various ways with increasing amount of solvent content in the solution phase. These selectivity orders have been explained by assuming solvent shared type of ion pair formation predominating in the resin phase in aqueous medium which changes over to the contact type in mixed solvent medium.

Introduction of a chelating group (iminodiacetic acid) into the styrene-divinylbenzene copolymer matrix is of a recent origin. The intrinsic dissociation constant of the monomeric unit is reported¹ to be in good agreement with the value reported² for the first acid dissociation constant of iminodiacetic acid. There are conflicting reports on the kinetics of exchange³⁻⁶ in this resin. The order of affinities of alkali ions has been given as $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ in aqueous medium. But the same in mixed solvent medium is not yet reported.

From the studies of monovalent cations on sulphonic acid⁷ and carboxylic acid⁸ types of exchangers in aqueous and mixed solvent media it has been inferred that the order of selectivities of the cations is governed by their capacities to form contact type of ion pairs with resin-sulphonate and solvent shared type of ion pairs with the resin-carboxylate in aqueous medium, while in mixed solvents, it is governed by their capacities to form contact type of ion pairs with both the resin anions. Similar studies have been carried out using a chelating resin in aqueous and mixed solvent media and the results are discussed below.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dowex chelating resin A-1, 50-100 mesh, was supplied by the Dow Chemical Company, Midland, Michigan, USA. This is a styrene-divinylbenzene copolymer within which are attached iminodiacetate groups. The actual cross-linkage is not known. However,

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Schwarz *et al.*,¹⁰ have reported the use of Dowex A-1 of 1% DVB. A polymeric mixture is leached from the low cross-linked resin¹¹. The breakdown of the resin has not been studied in detail. A sodium hydroxide treatment is recommended by the Dow Company¹² when the resin loses its exchange capacity due to long storage in the hydrogen form (according to Schwartz *et al.*,⁶ a possible explanation for this recommended procedure is the opening of the structure and removal of trapped soluble material when the resin is converted to the sodium form).

This resin can act as a base as well as an acid^{4, 13}. It exists both in the salt form as well as in acid form, due to the interaction of the imino group with the hydrochloric acid, used in its regeneration to H⁺ form. To prepare the acid form of this resin, Krasner and Marinaky¹ have suggested extensive washing of it with distilled water until the salt is completely hydrolysed.

In the present studies, the resin was prepared in the NH₄⁺ form following the same procedure as described earlier⁹.

The moisture content of the exchanger, estimated by heating a known quantity at 110 ± 2°C to constant weight was 24.6%. The exchange capacity of this wet resin was found to be 1.03 mequiv/g by treating a known quantity of it in a column with excess standard acid and titrating the excess acid⁹.

The alkali chlorides, 1-propanol, 2-propanol and acetone were BDH AnalaR reagents. The methanol and ethanol were distilled in the laboratory.

In the case of the chelating resin, the solution phase was always found to remain neutral after equilibration with the alkali salt solutions. This indicates negligible hydrolysis unlike in the case of carboxylic acid resin.

The procedure followed for the determination of selectivity coefficients in the presence of different amounts of organic solvents is the same as described earlier⁹. No correction has been applied either for the uptake of organic solvents by the resin or for the Donnan invasion of the resin by the electrolyte.

RESULTS

The selectivity coefficients of Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺ against NH₄⁺ obtained in aqueous and mixed solvent media are given in Table 1.

$K_{NH_4}^{Li^+}$ decreases continuously with increase of methanol, while with other solvents it remains the same up to about 30% and then increases resulting in the reversal of affinities of Li⁺ and NH₄⁺. $K_{NH_4}^{Na^+}$ and $K_{NH_4}^{K^+}$ increase continuously with increase of organic solvents, resulting in the reversal of affinities with respect to NH₄⁺.

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TABLE I

Exchange equilibrium coefficients* of Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ against NH_4^+ on the chelating resin, Dowex A-1.

$$K_{\text{NH}_4^+}^{\text{C}^+} = \frac{(\text{NH}_4^+) (\text{RC})}{(\text{C}^+) (\text{RNH}_4)}$$

Solvent	% organic solvent (V/V)	$K_{\text{NH}_4^+}^{\text{Li}^+}$	$K_{\text{NH}_4^+}^{\text{Na}^+}$	$K_{\text{NH}_4^+}^{\text{K}^+}$
Water	0	0.73	0.60	0.57
Water-methanol	10	..	0.60	0.60
	30	0.69	0.64	0.64
	50	0.65	0.70	0.72
	70	0.61	0.85	0.86
	90	0.58	1.17	1.23
Water-ethanol	10	..	0.64	0.60
	30	0.73	0.70	0.67
	50	0.81	0.85	0.82
	70	0.97	1.65	1.29
	90	2.04	7.00	7.58
Water-1-propanol	10	..	0.64	0.60
	30	0.73	0.70	0.67
	50	0.81	0.92	0.86
	70	1.08	1.71	1.43
	90	3.51	15.65	15.18
Water-2-propanol	10	..	0.64	0.60
	30	0.73	0.76	0.67
	50	0.86	1.03	0.95
	70	1.21	2.06	1.73
	90	7.86	30.48	21.28
Water-acetone	10	..	0.64	0.60
	30	0.73	0.70	0.67
	50	0.81	0.85	0.72
	70	0.97	1.22	0.95
	90	14.86	22.25	12.70

*Temperature 25°C; $(\text{C}^+) + (\text{NH}_4^+) = 0.020\text{M}$

The order of affinities of alkali ions in aqueous medium ($\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$) is, in general, reversed in the presence of sufficient organic solvent in the solution phase except that of Na^+ and K^+ in presence of 1-propanol, 2-propanol and acetone and that of Li^+ and K^+ in presence of acetone.

The exchange behaviour of alkali ions against NH_4^+ (on Dowex A-1) in aqueous and mixed solvent media is very similar to that on carboxylic acid type resin⁹ except for the following :

- (1) There is no decrease in $K_{\text{NH}_4^+}^{\text{Li}^+}$ with increase of organic solvents on the chelating resin except in methanol. During the increase of $K_{\text{NH}_4^+}^{\text{Li}^+}$ in the presence of other organic solvents, there is a reversal of affinities between Li^+ and NH_4^+ unlike with the carboxylate resin.
- (2) There is no reversal of affinities between Li^+ and K^+ on the chelating resin in presence of acetone.
- (3) In water-methanol medium, there is an increase of $K_{\text{NH}_4^+}^{\text{Na}^+}$ on the chelating resin unlike on the carboxylate resin.

DISCUSSION

The order of selectivities observed in aqueous medium, viz., $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ as well as the various reversals in the selectivity order in presence of mixed solvents can be explained, as in the case of carboxylic acid type resin⁹, on the basis that the order of affinities in aqueous medium is governed predominantly by the capacities of the cations to form solvent shared type of ion pairs with the resin iminodiacetate, while in mixed solvents, it is determined mostly by their capacities to form contact type of ion pairs.

Comparatively stronger ion binding of sodium than caesium to poly-acrylate observed by Gill *et al.*,^{14,15} as well as the different selectivity orders of alkali ions observed by Ti Tien¹⁶ on phosphonic acid resins at different pHs also lend support to the present authors' conclusions in addition to the evidences cited earlier⁹.

There is one interesting feature, however, with this exchanger in mixed solvent medium. The selectivity of Li^+ against NH_4^+ goes above unity in presence of organic solvents except in methanol. This has not happened either with carboxylic or with sulphonic acid type of exchangers.

The selectivity order $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ which is the reverse to that observed on sulphonic acid exchangers has been observed on phosphonic acid exchangers also. The influence of organic solvents on this exchanger is under investigation. This selectivity order offers possibilities of separation of small amounts of potassium from lithium salts as well as potassium from sodium salts. This aspect will be investigated after selecting the best resin which gives maximum selectivity differences and other favourable operating conditions like minimum swelling, minimum breakdown of the resin structure, etc.

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